

Summary Report on Stakeholder Involvement

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Purpose and scope of the deliverable

This report follows Report D2.1 Policies, Practices and Strategies. That initial report set out the policy framework for each of the Case Studies, examining national, regional and local strategies and influences. The subsequent involvement of Stakeholders sought to examine how those strategies and policies were experienced by those operating or residing in the Case Study areas; this report summarises the views expressed.

This is the second stage of the policy theme running through the three years of SPOT - the Social and Innovative Platform on Cultural Tourism and its Potential towards Deepening Europeanisation.

This Framework Paper consists of four parts:

- Part One:** The Summary Report on Stakeholder Involvement
- Part Two:** A background paper used in Chairs' briefings for the conduct of the Round tables. It describes sources of support (in policy and financial terms) for Cultural Tourism (Appendix A – Policy Instruments)
- Part Three:** A report describing the arrangements made by each partner for Stakeholder Involvement via Round Tables or appropriate substitutes (Appendix B)
- Part Four:** A list of the Stakeholders involved

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SUMMARY REPORT ON STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT (SPOT Deliverable D2.2)

1. Background

This report follows Report D2.1 Policies, Practices and Strategies. That initial report set out the policy framework for each of the Case Studies, examining National, regional and local strategies and influences. The subsequent involvement of Stakeholders sought to examine how those strategies and policies were experienced by those operating or residing in the Case Study areas and this report summarises the views expressed.

2. The Case Studies

The Case Studies investigated through SPOT are:

- Art Nouveau, Barcelona, Spain (ES)
- Buzau Carpathians and Sub-Carpathians, Romania (RO)
- The Cyclades, Greece (EL)
- Ida-Virumaa, Estonia (EE)
- Kinderdijk, Netherlands (NL)
- Komárom, Hungary (HU and/or HU-SK)
- Lusatia, Germany (DE)
- Ljubljana, Slovenia (SI)
- The Valley of Palaces and Gardens (Lower Silesia, Poland) (PL)
- Media Tourism, Scotland (UK)
- Nitra, Slovakia (SK)
- Piedmont Landscape and Literary Park, Italy (IT)
- Southern Moravia, Czechia (CZ)
- Styrian Iron Route, Austria (AT)
- Beit She'an Valley, Israel (IL)

Throughout this report, they will be referred to by their country letters (e.g. CZ). Where references are made to observations from particular case studies, they are illustrative rather than comprehensive (so if, for example two countries' initials show against a particular observation, it is not intended to suggest that no other stakeholders made the same or a similar point).

3. The Round Tables

3.1 CONCEPT OF THE ROUND TABLES

The prime purpose of the Round Tables was to identify those policies and mechanisms (at European, National, Regional and Local levels) which promote (or obstruct) the development of Cultural Tourism.

Further objectives were:

- i. To encourage the creation of new relationships between Stakeholders to address and develop Cultural Tourism.
- ii. To seek active engagement and support from Stakeholders for the SPOT project (and hence Cultural Tourism).
- iii. To give information to Stakeholders which may help them to develop the quality of the Cultural Tourism offerings.
- iv. To gain feedback on the SPOT project and its approach and effectiveness
- v. To ascertain whether the Stakeholders have questions which can be addressed by the huge amount of data gathered by SPOT, by the algorithms in the SPOT-IT tool and the web-based Resource Centre together with the policy insights.

Whilst Chair's notes were prepared for each Round Table (based on a core set of prompts, with specific targeted pointers for each Case Study deriving from the background work carried out and described in the following section), it was suggested that the discussion be allowed to follow the priorities of the stakeholders.

It was emphasised that the dialogue between partners was important and that new perspectives and new understandings would probably arise as stakeholders from different sectors and with different motivations were brought together to address common issues.

3.2 PREPARATION FOR THE ROUND TABLES

In advance of the Round Table meetings, partners prepared updates and further policy exploration (focused on the Case Studies) based on Report D2.1 Policies, Practices and Strategies (which described the policy framework), the intention being:

- i. To provide an updated statement of the policy context for the Case Study areas
- ii. To provide a more focused view of policy implications in the Case Study areas
- iii. To provide material to inform Stakeholders' round table discussions
- iv. To assess potential policy, financial and philosophical support to our existing Case Studies and to assist in future Cultural Tourism developments
- v. To gain a brief overview of responses to the coronavirus pandemic

The original report was based on the situation at Q1 2020 and the revisions were intended to update the policy framework to Q1 2021, allowing discussion of the two policy positions. As it transpired, the changes between the two quarters were much less marked than had been anticipated. Policy reviews were not high profile activities during the first year of the pandemic, due both to the number of employees not working in the office and to the fact that more urgent, short-term actions were necessary to deal with the situation under COVID-19. There were some changes due to political change and to a number of consequent political amendments to administrative structures and responsibilities. Nevertheless, the partners' policy observations were extremely pertinent and served to both shape and sharpen the round table deliberations and to provide a stronger focus on specific Case Study issues.

To act as background support to Chairs, a note of potential funding and support mechanisms was prepared and is attached as Appendix A

3.3 RESPONSE TO DIFFICULTIES POSED BY COVID-19

In view of the COVID-19 pandemic, it was felt necessary to consider the potential for conducting the round tables in physical form as originally envisaged. Following discussion with partners, the Project Management Board accepted a proposal to continue with round table meetings either in practice or by meeting virtually, depending on the state of local

regulations and the levels of infection in each partners' country.

It was agreed that Round Tables should be organised between 31st May and 9th July 2021. The increase in the pandemic in Spring 2021 led to a significant number of partners experiencing difficulty both contacting stakeholders and in making suitable live and on-line arrangements. Several requests were made to the Work Package Leaders to defer the deadline. Recognising the situation, a modest extension was considered, but it became clear that the cultural tourism industry was approaching its peak summer period. This was particularly important for businesses and representatives due to the terrible loss of income over the previous twelve months. The Project Management Board, at the request of the WP2 leaders, accepted that the new deadline for organising round tables should be after the peak period and it was agreed that round table reports should be submitted by 1st October. (Nevertheless, a small number of partners experienced continuing difficulties as the waves of infection moved through and asked for further extensions).

Partners made considerable efforts to either organise round tables (some virtual, some real and some hybrid) or to interview key Stakeholders individually. In some cases, a number of round tables were held, based on geography or specific interest groups.

A note describing the arrangements adopted for each Case Study is attached as Appendix B.

3.4 NUMBERS OF STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED

The agreed Work Programme for the action required the involvement of 'at least three stakeholders from each Case Study'. Contact with Stakeholders by academic partners varied considerably – some of the universities had long and continuing involvement with the Case Studies, others built relationships during the duration of the project. None however, had those relationships unaffected by COVID-19. Some local businesses had neither the time nor the inclination to discuss longer-term directions in their areas – survival was top of their agenda. Similarly with administrative and political representatives – their workload was often concerned with dealing with the pandemic and in many cases face-to-face contact to build/reinforce relationships was just not possible.

It is of great credit to the partners that so many were able to conduct round tables (or alternatives) at this stage in the project and to involve such a diverse range of Stakeholders. In total, between the 15 partners involved in Case Studies, 181 Stakeholders contributed to the deliberations.

The list of stakeholders is attached as Appendix C.

3.5 CONDUCT OF THE ROUND TABLES

Guidance was prepared to support the Chairs of the round tables, but there was no set format – it was stressed that the priorities of the Stakeholders should shape the discussion. It was suggested that Chairs should first check with participants their understanding of the term 'Cultural Tourism' – not so much to achieve a definition, but to clarify common and different perspectives amongst the Stakeholders for use in the later discussions.

Second, it was indicated that Chairs might briefly explore the impact of the pandemic - for two reasons, first the issue was likely to be uppermost in the minds of many Stakeholders and immediate problems needed to be aired to avoid them cropping up throughout the dialogue, but secondly to identify any longer-term changes (in thinking and activity) brought on by the impact of COVID-19.

From the earlier policy work, a number of themes had been identified and Chairs were asked to address any of these felt appropriate. In practice, the round tables (and interviews) managed to address effectively a large number of the themes – perhaps more than had been envisaged in setting up the round table approach.

3.6 COLLATION OF RESULTS

Partners put together extensive reports on the deliberations of the stakeholders, whether via real or virtual round tables or by personal interviews. These were submitted to the Aberdeen Team for processing.

4. The Discussions

4.1 UNDERSTANDING OF CULTURAL TOURISM

This was suggested as an initial brief topic to initiate the discussions and to establish broad areas of agreement and seek out more challenging points. In general, the round tables had little difficulty in reaching a sufficient consensus on the meaning of ‘Cultural Tourism’ to allow the discussions to move forwards. However, not all the round tables arrived at the same position – some were heavily focused on cultural artefacts and buildings, others on appreciation of nature or ‘wellness’, some were fundamentally based on the landscape and environment and an interesting dimension was the rise in importance of intangible heritage. But within each Case Study, there was a general recognition of the type of cultural tourism being discussed. It appeared that Stakeholders had a perception of what cultural tourism was *in their context* and the debates continued on that basis. Which is not to say that wider considerations were not explored – the section below on Innovation points to the view that cultural tourism was, in almost every case, subject to continuous review and development. An interesting point was that a number of the Stakeholders pointed to the need for education of local populations and businesses to understand not only the current state of cultural tourism in their areas, but also the potential for development.

4.2 CORONAVIRUS

The purpose of this section was to acknowledge the immediate problems, but not to explore the details of how cultural tourism activities needed to change in response to the pandemic or how those activities, businesses and institutions had been, and would be, affected by it. Rather, it was intended to explore how the context for cultural tourism had been changed by the pandemic and whether the pandemic’s effect had changed mindsets and aspirations.

I. FLEXIBILITY AND COPING MECHANISMS

- a. The pandemic had such a significant effect on local markets that fundamental or strategic responses had been necessary. A number of comments described

situations where relationships or procedures had been ossified prior to the pandemic and that a dynamic response had led to new ways of working. There were comments that, with the reduced pressure of day-to-day business during the height(s) of the pandemic, the opportunity had been taken to improve skills, to develop new business plans and generally to improve the fitness of organisations to meet the future (IT). In at least one case (CZ), a wide range of actors had been brought together to develop a new medium-term tourism strategy; in others, stakeholders had been driven to reappraise their markets (and sometimes to discover domestic or on-line markets which had previously been given a relatively low profile (ES, SI, IT). This diversification of tourism products was seen as having a longer-term impact on the nature of tourism generally and of cultural tourism in particular. Where efforts had been made to bring together tourism partners in the face of the pandemic, mutual support was seen as valuable (EE).

- b. Where previously tourism had been seen as a somewhat stable activity – a regular, if seasonal, flow of visitors with slowly-changing demands – the pandemic environment had favoured much more responsive businesses, seeking new markets to replace the old and able to adapt the tourism offering. There was little evidence that stakeholders were looking to ‘business as usual’ in the near or medium-term future. Indeed in at least one case (IT), a determination was expressed not to return to the pre-pandemic way of doing things. These new attitudes are not limited to the commercial sector. The receipt of pandemic recovery money has led to an increased capacity of municipalities to seek strategic change (PL); changing visitor requirements had led to public investment and proposed investment in appropriate facilities including existing and proposed new cycle routes (HU, DE, RO). In some areas with low tourist penetration, the recovery money had provided a level of stability previously missing (EE).
- c. In some Case Study areas (NL, EE, IT, UK), the issue of visitor management became significant, whether to deal with social distancing, greater pressure of domestic tourists etc. It appeared that new concepts were being developed to deal with the issues and that these might be beneficial for the future of cultural tourism.

II. TOURISM MARKET

- a. Unsurprisingly, most round tables and individual stakeholders had commented on the rise in domestic tourism. Whilst this had not provided a full replacement for missing international tourists, there was generally a sizeable and reliable flow of ‘local(ish)’ visitors. Whilst some stakeholders were looking towards the eventual return of international tourists, others (SI, ES) saw interesting new dimensions in catering for domestic visitors.
- b. One observation which appeared relatively common amongst stakeholders was that the balance had moved towards individual and family visitors. This was particularly noticeable where Case Study areas attracted tour groups or conference bookings (CZ, IT), but the implications for the provision of services was apparent in most areas. To some extent, the move towards domestic visitors had led to more short-term or day visits, with tourists using their own transport, but the implications for accommodation and package add-ons were noticeable. Restrictions on movement had further intensified the seasonality, shortened the tourist season and led to competition for dates between events (EE). One issue that had arisen was the very marked rise in prices to reflect the demands of the pandemic (IL)
- c. Many stakeholders pointed to an increased interest in outdoor and environmental tourism (again, this may be attributable, in part, to the increase in domestic visitors

and to the avoidance of more risky indoor activities).

III. FACILITIES

- a. A number of key facilities were identified as necessary in response to the pandemic. Cycling provision is mentioned above, but the need for good IT infrastructure was identified to support both visitor management (hotel, meal bookings etc., but also the provision of new services (video tours, improved advertising media etc., enhancements to museum and building visits) (CZ)
- b. The reduced flow (or even absence) of visitors meant that many businesses had taken the opportunity to repair/upgrade their facilities (PL).
- c. There was a demand from visitors for improved standards of hygiene and, whilst it was occasionally noted that large and/or chain hotels were highly disciplined in maintaining standards, tourists often indicated that they felt safer in smaller establishments. Whilst this was a matter of debate, no round table appeared to arrive at a set position on the issue.
- d. Not all facilities are provided by the public or private sector. There has been some loss of activity in the third (voluntary and citizen) sector. In part this is because older members of communities often play leading parts in driving this sector and older people have often felt less safe taking part in group activities; it is considered that a range of cultural activities (choirs, orchestras, language practice) have been particularly badly hit (DE). On the other hand, as people spent more time at home, the pandemic has had an effect of increasing the donation of significant cultural artefacts to museums as people had time to clear their houses (EE).

4.3 POLICY FORMULATION

In addressing the issue of Policy Formulation, round tables considered issues including 'Where is policy made? Who drives the policy? Do the relevant policies suitably address Cultural Tourism? In policy terms, is there a coherent relationship between Culture and Tourism?' The round tables were able to give some measure of the relationship between espoused policies (as described in SPOT report D2.1) and that experienced by stakeholders in the Case Study areas.

I. POLICY LEVELS AND INTEGRATION

- a. By way of background to the round table discussions, updates had shown that due to political change and Ministry reorganisations, Tourism in a number of the countries had been subject to significant change. Despite Tourism often being identified as an important economic sector, there was little evidence that the changes had raised the profile of Tourism or enhanced the potential for political backing for Cultural Tourism.
- b. This was a cause for comment in some of the round table discussions. A number of observations were made (SK,RO) that continuing political and/or administrative changes meant that it was difficult for consistent and coherent approaches to Cultural Tourism to be established in the lives and work of residents and stakeholders generally.
- c. The discussions demonstrated that, even where national policies were known to stakeholders (and there was considerable evidence that such knowledge was not universal), they were considered to have little impact (even relevance) locally. Regional and local/community policies were considered more important and local policies were generally acknowledged.
- d. A number of comments were made about the relevance/application of policies in

furtherance of cultural tourism. The absence of links between Tourism policies and Culture policies was a frequent observation (DE,RO), but for some stakeholders, the issue was much wider. In at least one case (CZ) lack of permissive legislation acted as a block to some aspects of policy development. Examples of policy (or its absence) in respect of approaches involving landscape/environment/land use were particularly striking, but the issue occurred in other forms of cultural tourism; that is the failure to join up policy between different ministries and departments and between different levels of government (EE). In some cases, there appeared to be considerable obstacles (at least in the short term) where progress required the coordination of policy between different agencies (NL,PL,DE) – there were references to the need for a holistic approach, which was seen as being quite complex to make a reality. This was demonstrated particularly starkly in the case of cross-border coordination where national approaches were not well aligned (HU-SK, EE).

- e. The importance of support, or otherwise, from (particularly) local politicians was seen by some stakeholders as key in shaping cultural tourism policy and practice at the local level (AT,SK). Also at the local level, some reservations were noted that, where public sector intervention had occurred to support cultural events, there may be a tendency for private initiatives to be more difficult to establish due to low financial viability in competition with free and heavily-subsidised public-fronted activities (EE).

II. INFLUENCING POLICY AND LINKS TO DEVELOPMENT POLICIES

- a. Even where stakeholders were aware of policies relating to their Case Study, the lack of continuing renewal and communication were seen as problematic. It was noted in report D2.1 that some policies were relatively historic (up to 15 years old) and had not been brought up-to-date to meet current conditions and local requirements (DE,HU). A further observation was that, not only are some policies outdated, but so are the laws framing the scope for policy development (CZ).
- b. In at least one case (ES), the area could be described as ‘over-policy-ed’ and the immediate problems had led to review and some consolidation, not least in coordinating timescales.
- c. There was little discussion amongst stakeholders about how to influence policy. Based on the discussions, the stakeholders were more interested in accessing finance (which is to some extent dependent on the policy framework) and the primary relationship was concerned with how activities could be presented to meet funding criteria. It was noted, however, that because ‘cultural tourism’ did not feature strongly (if at all) in regional or local policy statements, grant applications etc. tended to stress more mainstream terminology (EE,PL).
- d. A feature of those case studies based in low-income or weak economic areas is the strong dependence on EU programming documents. Stakeholders commented that there was little access to development funds outside the broad economic development frameworks set out in these documents and even relatively minor infrastructure developments were considered to be problematic. National funds were not aligned to complement EU funds in the field of cultural tourism (EE,RO,SK,CZ).

III. CAPACITY TO CHANGE PERSPECTIVES ON POLICY

- a. Amongst stakeholders in many of the case studies, one issue recurred (and recurred in a number of different forms). It relates to future policy. At the broadest level, clear statements were made about the re-evaluation by

stakeholders (including both business owners/managers and policy planners) of the economic considerations relating to the tourism agenda. Strong comments were made (ES, SI et al) that the unfettered pursuit of financial returns from tourism was having a detrimental effect on both local residents and on other agendas including green and environmental issues. A renewed focus on domestic tourism (and the increasing demand for outdoor/active tourism opportunities) appeared to be leading to diversification away from mass tourism. The drivers for this were from both business needs and from representations from local residents. Stakeholders appeared not to be attracted to mass tourism opportunities and referred to the low quality of service provision to cater to those markets ('trivial tourism offers' SI). It should be noted, however, that overall the stakeholders may be to some extent a self-selecting sample with a declared interest in cultural tourism.

- b. Stakeholders did identify a large range of opportunities presented by potential changes in policy to support cultural tourism. Opportunities include reduced seasonality (on the grounds that cultural tourism can take place outside the peak periods) (UK); better spread of visitors away from main centres (SI); possibility of longer, richer stays with deeper experiences (PL); perception of the area – high quality focus on cultural aspects can make a place an attractive venue and attract both new residents and complementary cultural activities and products (PL).
- c. A particularly strong theme was that policy should more reflect the needs of local residents and that local people should be more engaged in the creation of the cultural experiences on offer. These aspects are covered in the following section 'Local Engagement/Local Benefit'.

IV. DEVELOPING FUTURE POLICY

- a. Several of the round tables discussed the difficulties and opportunities for developing future policy on cultural tourism. The difficulties had three main sources. The first was a lack of knowledge of how to influence policy at every level. This included a lack of knowledge about timetables for policy review. The issue was highlighted by the lack of reference to 'cultural tourism' in planning documents.
- b. The second source of difficulty was the willingness of parties to cooperate to influence policy. Several cases were cited where private sector partners had not been invited to participate in policy review or, where they had been invited, had failed to engage. (SK,SI). A further comment was that neither industry nor academia are very engaged in developing cultural tourism (AT). Problems of engaging cross-border partners were noted (HU-SK), as were the difficulties posed by trying to integrate tourism and cultural agendas where these were structured differently (DE)
- c. The third source of difficulty is resources. This was not solely related to financial resources. In some cases, the personnel needed to coordinate/motivate policy development and implementation (including Local Action Groups) were absent (EE,CZ). However, the difficulty of identifying financial resources to develop cultural tourism was a common feature in many of the round tables. (This topic is explored further under Infrastructure and Implementation below).

4.4 LOCAL ENGAGEMENT/LOCAL BENEFIT

One of the aims of the SPOT project is 'to work with local communities, to empower them, and to put them in charge of cultural tourism through co-design with local stakeholders'. SPOT is particularly interested in forms of cultural tourism which

meet the needs and enhance the lives of people living in the vicinity of the attraction. For this Theme, round tables were asked to consider how local residents will benefit from the development of cultural tourism: is there local support for more cultural tourism? If there is local opposition to tourism, what arrangements are in place to mitigate the problems? Given that some tourist developments merely allow external operators to extract value from a locality, what mechanisms exist to ensure economic benefits accrue to local people? Are the arrangements for local consultation and 'ownership' (both practical and psychological) adequate?

I. PERCEPTION AND SELF-PERCEPTION

- a. A theme which resonated through many of the round tables/interviews was the importance of cultural tourism in uncovering or displaying significant elements of local identity and history. In some cases, it was considered that capturing history to show to visitors actually served to protect that history (EE). In rural areas particularly, local customs, traditions, music, language – even food - preserved those important roots for future generations: cultural tourism provides a vehicle for holding those dimensions in context (EL, DE, PL). A further comment was that much of the activity in this area comes from local volunteers; this provided both a focus (via local festivals etc.) and a means of social consolidation; it also served to engage local young people and recent residents with the cultural activities of the area (IT).
- b. With much effort expended in presenting local culture to the outside world, stakeholders commented that perhaps the main benefit was in local communities' perceptions of themselves – a recognition of what is unique and special appeared to engender local pride and to provide motivation to regard what they had as precious. The need to overcome a sense of isolation in communities was observed – 'people pass through, but we're not a destination', 'we're a peripheral community and can't survive without support' (IL). The importance of tangible and intangible cultural heritage was highlighted by stakeholders. Where that uniqueness was recognised by outside bodies – UNESCO World Heritage status was particularly valued (PL, IT, SI) – the impact on local communities was regarded as transformational. Indeed, in at least one case (IT), the uplift had been so marked that it was suspected former residents were being attracted back to the area as they started to value what the area had to offer.

II. QUALITY AND SERVICE PROVISION

- a. In part following on from the previous issue, stakeholders had remarked on the higher expectations from cultural tourists as compared to mass tourists - 'a more discerning audience'. With increased pride, local residents had started to raise standards and to demand, for example, higher levels of maintenance and cleaning (PL, SI). Better catering was required and in one case (NL) the local municipality had bought out and closed poor quality catering establishments and 'mass' souvenir shops in keeping with the ambience it wished to display. The net result is that local residents also benefit from a higher quality environment and improved service provision. One danger was pointed out here, that attractions and festivals are aimed at the tourist market and that the needs of local residents may be overlooked; this was not a feature in all Case Studies. An interesting point raised by a stakeholder is that the maintenance of quality standards is dependent on 'attention to detail' – and nobody pays more attention to detail

than very local residents who need to be actively engaged (SI).

- b. A second key issue pointed out by stakeholders was that sometimes local services (which otherwise may become unviable) were sustained by the addition of tourist numbers to existing local demand. Transport and health services were particularly quoted (DE).

III. CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT

- a. Mechanisms for citizen engagement were very different in different Case Study areas (and even in different parts of some Case Study areas). Some stakeholders commented that either no engagement (on tourism or specifically cultural tourism) took place (CZ, AT), or that where there were attempts to develop dialogue, it was generally uncoordinated and dependent on initiatives from one public institution or commercial enterprise (SK). In some cases, local people had a low perception of their area and so displayed little interest in working together to present it to the outside world (UK,CZ). In others, active citizen engagement was noted in, for example, wine tours and folklore festivals (again CZ!)
- b. In some however, regular surveys of residents' perceptions took place (SI), active use of social media (NL) engaged local communities on relevant issues. It was recognised that active citizen engagement would be needed if areas really were to transform from somewhat passive recipients of general tourism traffic to places where cultural tourism was an active and integrated component of local life and vitality (ES). The lack of suitable organisations to promote the interests of local residents in these situations was noted (SI) and tackling the dis-benefits of tourism was seen to require more political leverage in the form of local resident mobilisation and organisation.

IV. EMPLOYMENT AND LOCAL CREATION

- a. Whilst few stakeholders appeared to reference cultural tourism as a driver of increased employment in service industries (catering, accommodation, translation etc.), considerable attention was paid to self-employment in the creative industries and in active holidays. There were many references to arts and crafts enterprises based on local culture and skills, with strong support for 'housing' craft workers in common workshops where a critical mass of such activities would provide an attraction to cultural tourists (DE, IT). An issue was identified with the strong commercial focus on tourism in that marketing often determined what products are stocked in souvenir shops etc., to the detriment of local craft producers who found it difficult to compete and trade (SI). The hope was that more focus on cultural tourism would open up markets for local craft workers. In some cases, the volume of tourist traffic was not sufficient to genuinely expand business profitability and employment (IL).

V. CULTURE AS A BRIDGE

- a. In terms of social cohesion, cultural activities (including ballet, music, food) were seen as having a contribution to make in bringing together disparate ethnic and linguistic groups living locally. Sharing festivals, working on local crafts, recognising one another's strengths and having an external audience to 'present to' was seen by some stakeholders as a potential means of integrating different sections of society, but active work was needed to make this a reality (EE, HU-SK). In the absence of positive intervention and recognized standards, there was the possibility that cultural differences would lead to misunderstandings (EE)

4.5 SHARED VISION

As an introduction to the round table discussions, it was suggested that participants be asked to describe what they saw as ‘Cultural Tourism’ (and this tended to be in the context of the individual Case Study). In general, stakeholders appeared to have little difficulty in agreeing between themselves what cultural tourism meant for them and there was only occasional evidence of tensions or misunderstandings arising from different perspectives. This was assuredly not the case in terms of the vision for the area. Most round tables commented that a significant problem for the development of cultural tourism was the inability to define a Shared Vision for the area and some referred to the lack of suitable leadership and/or structures to own a ‘Vision’. The focus of cultural tourism differed enormously between the different Case Studies (and seemed only tangentially to reflect the stakeholders’ roles and interests). Even in those cases where the ‘Vision’ may have been shared by stakeholders, priorities for investment, training, communication etc. sometimes differed. (These issues are covered in other sections). (‘One thing we all agree on, is that nobody agrees on anything’ (ES)).

I. WHAT IS ‘CULTURAL TOURISM’ FOR?

- a. The basis for a vision is an agreement on what stakeholders are seeking to achieve in the short, medium and longer terms. Whilst there were many different objectives expressed during the round tables, the short-term issue (to deal with damage to local economies due to the coronavirus) was relatively straight-forward. Looking forward, however, the range of options was very wide – to raise the standard of the tourist offer; to provide employment for people in the cultural industries; to give local people more say over the nature of tourism; to preserve local cultural heritage; to preserve local buildings and artefacts; to promote domestic tourism; to promote international tourism; and the rest. The round tables were able to identify a vast range of benefits of cultural tourism and it is perhaps not surprising that, with so many potential objectives, it is difficult for stakeholders with diverse perspectives to focus on a single Vision. Yet the mechanisms/organisations to assist in clarifying a vision were commented on more by their absence than their existence. A number of round tables suggested that citizen surveys/engagement would assist in narrowing the focus (IT, CZ), but few examples were quoted of it actually happening. There was little evidence of the round tables seeking to place cultural tourism within a wider context of tourism or broader economic regeneration.

II. WHOSE VISION?

- a. Because the objectives were, in general, only loosely defined, the stakeholders were not clear on who should own the vision; there were many comments about the lack of dialogue between interested organisations and in particular about the apparent division between the public and private sectors (this was interpreted variously as the authorities’ failure to engage entrepreneurs or the observation that small business owners did not respond to overtures from the consultative mechanisms (CZ, SK, UK, SI)). In the few cases where ownership of the vision was seen as in the hands of a particular body or bodies, the perception of stakeholders was that this was a ‘top-down’ approach (and possibly ‘bureaucratic’) which did not sufficiently recruit the necessary players to make progress happen (CZ, SI, RO, SK).

- b. A feature mentioned in a number of the round tables was the mismatch between local residents' perceptions of their locale with the 'image' in the minds of visitors (IT)
- c. Nevertheless, ideas on the nature of a vision did emerge. For some, the vision was in the form of a 'marketing plan' – the need to identify agreed target markets, to be clear about which tourists would meet the requirements and to design local facilities to attract and satisfy those segments (DE, UK, HU, NL). For others, the vision was about 'who we are' – what are our local values? How do we want to present ourselves to the outside world? In these cases, the vision was seen as a potential unifying vehicle, bringing together disparate interests or consolidating local identity (EE, RO). In practice, most Case Studies showed elements of each; in some, the two poles were quite clearly the cause of competition/difficulty in defining direction (NL, IT, AU, DE). A useful concept was brought forward by one round table which described 'cultural call words' - a word or words which encapsulated some aspect of local culture (a particular building style or a local societal attribute, for example) which could be used as shorthand (meme?) to promote the area to visitors, but which also contained meaning for local residents (HU).

III. CREATING A NEW VISION

- a. A number of stakeholders dwelt on the possibility of creating a vision (or a revised vision) for the Case Study area. Sometimes this was based on key features which needed to be emphasised and/or packaged to tell a 'story' (NL, HU). On other occasions, stakeholders were able to point to examples of visions in other places which they wished to copy - or avoid! (EE, UK). It was noticeable that in a number of Case Study areas, stakeholders pointed to implementation and coordination organisations as being effective in bringing partners together, but lacking the capacity to create and communicate an overall vision (CZ, RO, HU, DE, SK).
- b. In one case (IT), stakeholders addressed the issue of creating a new vision (to replace a long-standing stereotype of the region) and noted the considerable difficulty of making a replacement - possibly losing habitual visitors or failing to meet their expectations whilst a new identity was established.
- c. Difficulties of creating an identity or vision across national boundaries were seen as an issue where the two sides had different drivers, different timescales and lacked cross-boundary mechanisms to develop a shared way forward (HU-SK).
- d. Changing a vision is seen as a long-term activity – perhaps a generation or more. The role of school visits was seen by some as important in this regard, but also the existence of long-term institutions with the changed vision as a core belief (IT)
- e. A strong message came from the round tables that public consultation would be needed to really establish a shared message and this was followed up in one or two round tables with the observation that a major public education exercise would be needed to elucidate the benefits of cultural tourism, to explore the implications for local people and to engage residents in developing the cultural experience for visitors (RO, UK, IT).

4.6 SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT/GREEN AGENDA

Stakeholders were invited to address the issue of sustainable development in the context of cultural tourism, together with the relevance of the Green Agenda for activities in their Case Study area. Of all the issues considered by the round tables, this topic revealed the greatest spread of experiences between (but not within) the Case

Study areas. Whilst the responses were somewhat coloured by the experience of the pandemic (most remarked that this agenda had merited less attention than basic survival of businesses and institutions), the round tables considered a wide range of issues and were able to look to future implications. In particular, whilst sustainability had immediately a lower profile, stakeholders were keen to note the changing priorities of residents and visitors.

I. HOW IMPORTANT IS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND THE GREEN AGENDA?

- a. Regardless of the impact of the coronavirus, for some stakeholders, environmental considerations had not yet registered with local people – particularly in some post-industrial areas, the over-riding concern was for jobs and the local economy and the green agenda was seen as a constraint on that priority (EL, EE). Sometimes, despite public information campaigns and other actions, local residents had not responded (AT, UK, EE). Even where funding was available, attitudes were proving hard to change. Where strong sustainability strategies were in place, failure to implement them had not led to the desired impact.
- b. On the other hand, some areas reported enthusiastic adoption of environmental and green issues (ES, SK). Where this was the case, these concerns were addressed at every level, whether policies and practices adopted by local administrations, principles for organising street events and festivals or the leisure pursuits followed by local residents. In these cases, cultural tourism was an integral element of the overall approach.
- c. As elements of the context for cultural tourism, some areas were concerned with the maintenance and improvement of landscapes (as a feature of the tourism ‘offer’), together with nature protection measures. Interestingly, these provided a potential factor in the development of cultural tourism, but cultural tourism did not appear to be an explicit motivating factor in these cases (PL,RO).
- d. One factor mentioned in a number of round tables was that young people placed a higher value on environmental and green issues than their ‘more mature’ fellow residents. Another was that making experiences available to all meant that more attention needed to be paid to disabled access and facilities (PL).

II. IMPACT ON CULTURAL TOURISM

- a. A common factor pointed out by stakeholders was that, even where good environmental and green policies were in evidence, they almost invariably failed to mention Cultural Tourism. This contrasted with a number of comments made by stakeholders that they considered the environmental agenda and Cultural Tourism were wholly congruent – indeed cultural tourism itself could be seen as a countervailing pressure moderating the impact of mass tourism.
- b. The pressure for sustainability did not come solely from local residents or legislation. A number of round tables observed that tourists (and particularly cultural tourists) were expecting – even demanding – green policies in the areas they visited and in the services with which they were provided. (DE, IT). It was noted that businesses are relatively quick to respond to the changing demands, and that the public sector needs to embrace these opportunities. Strong identification with the green agenda was seen, not only to benefit existing visitors, but as a potential factor to attract future tourists. Cultural tourism also had the capacity to increase understanding of environmental issues, through thematic exhibitions, for example (EE).
- c. The conflict between tourism and environmental protection was a feature of a number of the round table discussions; in particular the effect of motor traffic

(both on- and off-road) was seen to have a negative impact on both residents and natural environments (RO, IT). One response was that the availability of e-cycles had served to reduce some of these pressures and in one case (IT), the poor local road infrastructure was seen as a bonus in that it reduced the capacity for tourist coaches, further encouraging the use of more ecological modes of transport.

III. MOTIVATORS FOR PURSUING SUSTAINABILITY AS PART OF A CULTURAL TOURISM STRATEGY

- a. Some of the Round tables addressed the pursuit of sustainability either as part of cultural tourism or to support cultural tourism. The first aspect – already mentioned – is that a green agenda can attract tourists, but, perhaps of more interest in the cultural tourism world, it can attract particular types of tourist. There were mentions that the type of tourist who appreciates a sustainable and ecologically sound experience is also likely to be one with more disposable income and who is willing to pay for higher standards. If the volume of tourists reduces (due to responses to the pandemic or to pressure from local residents), higher- value tourists can help to bridge the gap (DE, SI).
- b. Some stakeholders considered that enforced standards and other incentives were necessary to make progress on environmental issues, but others found that public education campaigns had an effect over time (RO, SK).
- c. The one motivator which might be expected to have an impact is money. This appeared not to be the experience of the stakeholders. There were many comments that finance for the Green Agenda is not well targeted and that the lack of specific mention of Cultural Tourism means that it is difficult to access relevant funding streams and, in particular, that it is difficult to access sufficient funds to make a significant difference, particularly where extensive capital investment is required (NL).
- d. What did appear to be a useful motivator was the existence of awards (at local, national or international levels). The recognition of achievement in the field reflected back on residents and businesses and became part of the identity which they then chose to emphasise to the outside world (SK).

4.7 INNOVATION

Tourism is a competitive market. One of the aims of SPOT is to encourage an innovative approach to cultural tourism, in particular by identifying good examples of innovation and by assisting stakeholders to support and develop appropriate innovative ideas and approaches. The potential for innovation is to be assessed against the policy environment and exemplified, where possible, using evidence from the case studies. A comment made in a number of the round table events was that the impact of coronavirus had made a significant change in the search for innovative responses and to the speed with which responses were implemented. To some extent, this had led to a more inventive, more responsive mindset which would be of value to organisations and businesses in the future. Against this, some stakeholders felt they were so exhausted trying to keep businesses running that they had little time or energy to try new approaches and the immediate issue was survival.

For the purposes of the project, SPOT had identified the following classifications as a means of understanding innovation:

- ***Incremental Innovation***. This involves taking an existing idea and positioning it in a new setting - for example by partnership working between stakeholders in different environments to look for 'good / best practice'. It could also involve a

modified idea using the same setting - for example by working with existing tourist facilities to expand horizons by introducing new client groups or additional services.

- **Radical Innovation.** This represents an entirely new development – a new attraction or finding a new way to present a concept to attract a completely new user base e.g. a forest becomes a venue for learning traditional woodworking crafts.
- **Transformational Innovation.** Innovation is made possible or instigated by external events/changes e.g. climate change discovers artefacts previously hidden or a new political or regulatory regime makes new types of cultural tourism possible.

Stakeholders referred to a very wide range of initiatives and innovative ideas for the future. The following section does not seek to list all the ideas in detail, but rather seeks to demonstrate how the practical measures point to more general approaches appropriate to the setting for other cases. Further information on the innovations can be obtained by reference to the individual Case Studies.

I. INCREMENTAL INNOVATION

This can be a 'safe' (i.e. low-risk), relatively low-cost, means of improving a service or business. It is mostly achieved by the organisation or business itself as part of regular management practices, but can be extremely important in improving the responsiveness and effectiveness of the enterprise. Examples cited by the round tables included:

- Better focus on the needs of domestic visitors (ES)
- 'Story-telling' to reflect a new focus on environmental and climate priorities (NL)
- Ensuring visitors see different dimensions to promote further visits (e.g. somebody visiting a venue for a wedding may be encouraged to return to explore its historical and cultural significance) (HU)
- Providing bicycles to encourage visitors to stay longer (and take their time to explore cultural attractions) in a tourist area (DE)
- Combined tickets to integrate travel offers or to link different attractions (SI/IT)
- Develop year-round tourism offers with local providers (DE)
- Tailor-made tours to attract and cater for smaller groups and domestic visitors (SI)
- On-line selling of existing products (SI)
- Prebooking system for visitors (for safety and for visitor management, including car parking) (UK, NL)
- Pre-booking system to allow 'wait' times where visitors can be sold other services (tours, café services, cultural information etc.) (UK, IT)
- Improved signage in relevant languages (IL, RO, SK)
- More self-service facilities (especially for food and drink) due to lack of sufficient staff (CZ)
- Workshops in the open air (IL)

II. RADICAL INNOVATION

Radical innovation can also be self-generated (although examples quoted in the round tables included innovations developed in collaboration between existing service providers and those stimulated by contact with other organisations in different networks). Community-based innovation can be stimulated by successful public engagement exercises in which a wide range of ideas interacting can be creative; in some Case Studies stakeholders reported that influential individuals (a local figurehead or a politician) were the source of change. Radical innovation – because it is something new – usually involves investment from the enterprises involved. Examples cited by the round tables included:

- Rafting on a local river (RO)
- Community-based arts events (RO)
- Promotion of recent historical events and buildings ('within living memory') for nostalgia tourism (EE)
- Exploration of historical trade routes to bring out the connections between neighbouring countries (NL)
- Bringing back traditional experiences (characteristic modes of transport, local specialised crafts etc.) (DE, PL)
- Citizens' bus driven by local volunteers and providing links to attractions, cycling routes etc. (DE)
- Combining original and local products from different producers to make a complete regionally-identifiable gourmet experience (PL)
- Enlarging the experience of a historical building by incorporating forest walks, cycle trails to give visitors a sense of the environment enjoyed by the building and its former occupants (UK)
- Re-use of existing buildings for wider tourism provision (EE)
- Linking themed experiences to neighbouring communities to give visitors a reason to stay longer (SK)
- Promotion of, for example, bird watching to attract a wider range of visitors and to spread the visitor season (CZ, IL)
- Use of out-of-season facilities, for example ponds for winter ice-skating (CZ)

III. TRANSFORMATIONAL INNOVATION

Transformational innovation requires stimulation by an outside agency – examples include climate change (opening up new possibilities), legislative or technological change, for example a change in planning policy to legalise home accommodation for visitors or new technology availability to introduce new services or media opportunities. Public sector intervention is a frequent source of transformational innovation by the introduction of policy opportunities and/or funding.

Transformational information has been described as 'game-changing' – the barriers preventing certain courses of action may be removed and new opportunities may be created. Examples cited by the round tables included:

- Use of new technology (this had a wide range of responses – 'if you haven't 'selfied' it, you haven't done it', 'once you've experienced something digitally, you will want to try it in real life'). There were numerous examples of digitally-guided tours (real and virtual) and a very common complaint that,

where the most important cultural experiences were, access to phone and broadband was at its worst (ES, DE etc.)

- The opportunity to use media to build links to ‘related experiences’ locally and in neighbouring areas to deepen and broaden the cultural offer (EE, IT, EL). Media were also used to ‘prepare’ visitors to appreciate the depth of experience which was on offer (NL,IT)
- Production of new revenue models to support maintenance and development of landscapes and natural resources (NL)
- Tax reliefs and interventions (ES, EE)
- Development of cultural areas in less-visited parts of towns and cities to spread the tourism load and benefit (SI)
- Creation of ‘cultural night tourism’ to link parks and the city (IL)
- Creation of premises where a range of different cultural crafts can be housed providing both support for craft workers and acting as an attraction for visitors to see craft products being produced (PL, SI)
- Revival of historical and traditional crafts and hosting of relevant fairs and events (PL)
- The award of status such as World Heritage site or identification of Intangible Cultural Heritage (IT)
- Identification of a European Cultural Route (HU-SK)
- Regional Fairs or cultural events brought together by regional or other administrations (IT)
- In addition there are many infrastructure interventions which can have Transformative impact. These are addressed in the next section.

IV. EDUCATION FOR INNOVATION

A point raised by a number of the stakeholders was for the need to promote an innovative environment. Education featured highly in these discussions and it was clear that training and education can feature at enterprise level, by cooperation amongst organisations with similar interests or by external intervention. The role of universities was identified by a small number of stakeholders. Examples cited by the round tables included:

- Training for licensed tourist guides (SI)
- University education for the development of tourism products (design thinking, project management, logistics etc.) (SK)
- Education of local populations (by exhibitions etc.) to appreciate cultural heritage, the importance of nature and landscape protection etc. (NL)
- Education of residents on the potential benefits from expanding cultural tourism (RO)
- Training for employees in service occupations (AT)
- Training for employers in developing new cultural tourism offers (AT)

4.8 INFRASTRUCTURE/POLICY MIX

To some extent the positive infrastructure issues which were addressed are covered in the section above on Innovation; round tables were able to examine some of the

barriers to cultural tourism progress in describing the infrastructure issues they identified. The stakeholders were, in general, very engaged with the issues and did not focus on negative aspects; nevertheless, by looking at what is needed to advance cultural tourism, it is unsurprising that they addressed omissions. Round tables examined both individual elements of infrastructure and the broad policies which covered them; they identified priorities and the inter-relationship between the elements.

I. TRANSPORT

Stakeholders addressed transport as a means of accessing the Case Study area (including by international travellers) and transport within the area to allow visitors to explore cultural attractions. In the main, the conclusion was that road transport – and particularly the road network – was a barrier in most areas to extending cultural tourism. Car parking limitations were evident (NL, UK). The limitations of private car availability for potential visitors was seen as a problem (DE), but more generally, the lack of useful public transport featured highly (UK, SI, DE, EE). The provision of public transport was not only insufficient, but its lack of availability in the evenings posed a particular issue for visits to cultural events, such as concerts, and to restaurants etc.

Against this, many stakeholders pointed to improved (and projected) cycling facilities as a major contributor to visitor mobility.

II. ACCOMMODATION

In a few areas (EE, HU-SK, UK, AT, IL) there were comments not only about the lack of accommodation, but, where it did exist, the quality was less than might be attractive to cultural tourists. There were some comments about the lack of coordination between accommodation providers, but generally it was considered that improving use of information technology would make the best use of the accommodation that does exist. One comment was that the increased focus on domestic tourists (and hence more likely day visitors) had reduced some accommodation pressures.

III. SANITATION

Perhaps given a higher profile by dealing with health issues during the pandemic, sanitation featured strongly in round table discussions. In some cases the provision of adequate water to heavily trafficked parts of towns and cities was a concern – particularly where attempts to change the flow of visitors might put additional demands on marginal services. Introducing visitors to areas with no water services clearly posed problems (RO). Of major concern however, was the provision of sewerage and other disposal services (RO, PL, UK). Increasing numbers of visitors put an additional strain on limited facilities – the investment decisions to improve infrastructures to maintain standards are not generally tied to awareness of tourism trends; this has a significant effect on both visitors and residents.

IV. OTHER TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE

The over-riding message coming from stakeholders was about the lack of coordination between the different elements of the tourism infrastructure – developing one aspect without regard to the whole picture inhibited progress (e.g. how useful is it to invest in cycling infrastructure if appropriate accommodation/ restaurants are missing?).

Some stakeholders pointed to the problems caused by the inability to attract sufficient staff to support tourism services (CZ, AT, UK). The issue is not only the lack of trained

staff (training can be provided), but the lack of staff willing to work in service industries due to the perceived unattractiveness of those occupations.

A pertinent comment was that a low number of tourists do not provide sufficient pressure on administrations (or businesses) to make the necessary investments to support cultural tourism as a proposition (EE, RO, IL) and as a result, areas lack suitable signage, visitor centres and all the basic elements necessary for a good visitor experience.

Where there are strong competing influences (between different types of visitor, organisations with different objectives, resident interests etc.) (NL, ES) it can be difficult to prioritise investments and that competition can, in itself, be a bar to progress.

4.9 IMPLEMENTATION

Even with a sound policy framework, progress to develop cultural tourism relies on good structures, clear priorities and effective delivery of infrastructure elements. Round tables discussed the opportunities and problems experienced in each of the Case Study areas.

I. LEADERSHIP

The lack of adequate leadership was a feature of many of the discussions, but in only a few cases did this refer to individuals (where individuals were commented on, it was more that nothing happened unless key individuals took an interest than that identified individuals had not acted appropriately). The main thrust of the debates was the lack of organisational structures concerned with delivery. Some stakeholders looked to national governments for effective action (EL), where others pointed to the weakness (often lack of resources or unclear remits) of local delivery mechanisms (CZ, RO, AT,EL). A particularly strong response related to the low capacity of local administrations to provide the necessary leadership (EL, EE, IL) and which, for many, were where they might have expected strong leadership, or, at least, a strong focus on local issues; this, together with problems of dialogue between public and private sector entities (CZ, SI, SK) led to slow, or non-existent, progress.

A very positive stance was taken in some Case Study areas, where local people and businesses had taken the attitude that, in the absence of action from the formal structures (made worse during the pandemic), 'we're going to have to do it ourselves' (EL, DE), including by initiatives from volunteers.

In quite a number of Case Study areas, there was a sense that, despite coordination and/or cooperation in some aspects, 'Cultural Tourism' was not perceived as an entity (with at least one exception (RO)), so it was difficult to draw together coordinated action across the full range of necessary attributes.

II. POLITICS

There is a clear link between leadership and the political environment, but stakeholders made a number of observations related to political processes in their own area. Some made the point that, if cultural tourism does not 'fit' with the political direction chosen by those in power, it can be extremely difficult to put together comprehensive packages to support it (PL, CZ); where areas are subject to frequent political change, some stakeholders described the difficulties of maintaining consistent long-term approaches to the development of cultural tourism. The political power of local residents is an important factor in the priorities

accorded to different aspects of cultural tourism (NL, ES, RO).

III. IMPLEMENTATION PLANS

Even where priorities were clear, the lack of clear strategies or formal plans for implementation were a common feature picked up by the round tables (PL, UK). There was optimism where plans do exist (SK). A further issue was that plans are sometimes so broad and under-funded, that competition for limited resources between different organisations is sometimes an obstacle to progress (DE, SI).

IV. FUNDING FOR CULTURAL TOURISM

- a. There were many, very thoughtful, contributions relating to funding. In low- resource Case Study areas there were comments that progress is not possible without the introduction of external funding (HU_SK, CZ, SI). Other areas found a lack of willingness by both public and private bodies to invest in cultural tourism (AT, EE). Of particular concern was that resources contributing to cultural tourism are often in different budgets and the complexity of bringing together those resources (often with competing timescales and in different organisations) was considered to be a real barrier. Even where developments could be funded from capital budgets, stakeholders commented on the difficulty of finding revenue to maintain those capital developments in the longer term (DE, RO).
- b. Others looked to different mechanisms to fund progress. Whether by new regional investment models to fund environmental approaches (NL) or by responding to market failure (for social sector activity) through new arrangements with banks and financial institutions (IT), new approaches to funding are being developed.
- c. Whilst there were many comments about the lack of coordination between public and private organisations, one issue in particular was not being addressed at a strategic level. Particularly in the wake of the pandemic, public bodies were trying to support local economies by investing in new or bigger festivals and events, often with free entry. This had at least two significant effects. On the one hand, there were occasionally too many competing events and attendances had fallen; on the other hand, the effect of free-entry public events had made some private sector events unviable (DE, EE).

4.10 MONITORING AND EVALUATION

In general, the stakeholders taking part in the round tables were fairly passive in relation to data to assist the progress of cultural tourism. Many showed awareness of the data that was available (quoting national statistics or bodies which hold data). Often references were made to the information they need to provide, rather than that required by them to run their operations. There were few, if any, strong demands for specific information that they felt was missing.

Observations made by the round tables included:

- Because we don't recognise 'Cultural Tourism' as an entity, we fail to collect specifically-relevant data; policy effectiveness is not monitored
- There is little collection of information about day visitors and, perhaps related, very little about non-paying visitors (the lack of a transaction does not trigger a data point)

- Elements of data collected by different organisations are not generally collated and there was little evidence of interpretation which would be of value to cultural tourism
- Information on communal monuments was collected (PL)
- Some information is collected on specific activities (e.g. cycling, health tourism (DE)).

5. Overall Observations

This overall exercise involving Stakeholders sought to examine how the expressed strategies and policies were experienced by those operating or residing in the Case Study areas. This report has sought, not to interpret observations, but to present the real voice of the stakeholders.

Whilst it was noted that, in general, most Stakeholders were not focused on (or able to quote) the policy statements of national or regional administrations so far as they relate to cultural tourism, they were able to describe some of the resultant impacts quite effectively. Policy statements do not always – even, rarely! - translate neatly into action on the ground; the stakeholders explored where the discontinuities led to poor implementation, but were also able to set out areas for improvement (almost always relating directly to issues in the Case Study areas).

The themes described are:

- Policy Formulation
- Local Engagement/Local Benefit
- Shared Vision
- Sustainable Development/Green Agenda
- Innovation
- Infrastructure/Policy Mix
- Implementation
- Monitoring and evaluation

Each theme had specific relevance in each Case Study area – some exhibited strengths, others pointed to discontinuities – but the need for each to be present at an adequately effective level demonstrated that cultural tourism needs more than a strong policy drive. Actions need to take place in many spheres – (coherent actions between the spheres would be a particular bonus) – if the promise of Cultural Tourism is to be realised in our cities, towns and communities.

Appendix A Policy Instruments (Background information for Chairs of Round Tables)

Policy Instruments relevant for the development of Cultural Tourism policy and practice

This initial list of policy instruments is set out by institution:

EUROPEAN UNION

Key relevant areas for Cultural Tourism policy are:

- I. European Regional Development Fund
- II. Cohesion Fund
- III. European Social Fund
- IV. Common Agricultural Policy
- V. Response to the coronavirus pandemic

With some exceptions, the impact of these policy directions will be identified within national and regional policies (covered in Section B of the updating process) and in the relevant programming documents. They are provided here as a checklist, having regard to the fact that *a mid-term review in 2025 will determine if changes in the programmes are needed for the last two years of the funding period and this may provide an opportunity to bend programmes to support Cultural Tourism.*

Regional Development and Cohesion Policy 2021-27
[\(https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/2021_2027/\)](https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/2021_2027/)

The main objectives driving EU investments in 2021-2027 are:

- *Regional development investments will strongly focus on Objectives 1 and 2. 65% to 85% of ERDF and Cohesion Fund resources will be allocated to these priorities, depending on Member States' relative wealth.*
- *Smarter Europe*, through innovation, digitisation, economic transformation and support to small and medium-sized businesses
- a Greener, carbon free Europe, implementing the Paris Agreement and investing in energy transition, renewables and the fight against climate change
- a more *Connected Europe*, with strategic transport and digital networks
- a more *Social Europe*, delivering on the European Pillar of Social Rights and supporting quality employment, education, skills, social inclusion and equal access to healthcare
- a *Europe closer to citizens*, by supporting locally-led development strategies and sustainable urban development across the EU.

Within these broad themes, there are some elements which may be particularly relevant for the development of Cultural Tourism, for example:

- The ERDF supports the competitiveness, sustainability and quality of tourism at regional and local levels.

- Interreg – with the possibility to develop inter-regional and cross-border operations. Additionally, the European Cross-Border Mechanism is introduced to harmonise relevant legal frameworks.
- Smart Specialisation Strategies can have a particular emphasis on Cultural and Creative Industries and Natural Heritage. (<https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/cultural-creative-regional-ecosystems>) Nine of SPOT's partner countries are registered for RIS3 Smart Specialisation approaches which can give added leverage to funding/policy change at regional, national and EU levels.

European Social Fund post-2020

Focusing on Social Rights, the Fund aims to strengthen social inclusion and to tackle inequality, with a particular emphasis on and civil society- and community-based organisations. There are implications for Cultural Tourism including in local economic development, training, social inclusion and support to left-behind communities.

Common Agricultural Policy 2021-2027

https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/key-policies/common-agricultural-policy/future-cap/key-policy-objectives-future-cap_en#nineobjectives

The key objectives set out for the new period are:

- to ensure a fair income to farmers;
- to increase competitiveness;
- to rebalance the power in the food chain;
- climate change action;
- environmental care;
- to preserve landscapes and biodiversity;
- to support generational renewal;
- vibrant rural areas;
- to protect food and health quality.

Within these objectives, there is considerable opportunity to enhance the economic and environmental impact of Cultural Tourism approaches.

LIFE

The 2021+ LIFE programme will cover the following areas:

- Nature and biodiversity
- Circular economy and quality of life
- Climate change mitigation and adaptation
- Clean energy transition

In addition an expanded Integrated Projects programme will address large-scale environment and climate projects. 7 of SPOT's partners are in affected countries.

European Green Deal 2019-24

To include the Just Transition Mechanism https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal/actions-being-taken-eu/just-transition-mechanism_en which seeks to support those areas most impacted by the move to a green economy.

Response to the Coronavirus Pandemic

A wide range of measures (many relevant for Cultural Tourism and development) are introduced to tackle economic and social issues arising as a result of the pandemic. Actions in several areas including the cultural sector are supported through the Coronavirus Response Investment Initiative https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/newsroom/coronavirus-response/ as part of Cohesion Policy and implemented through the Member States.

The Coronavirus Dashboard <https://cohesiondata.ec.europa.eu/stories/s/4e2z-pw8r> describes some of the broad measures being implemented through national and regional actions.

Council Resolution on a coordinated approach to travelling and travellers during the pandemic (13/10/2020) https://ec.europa.eu/info/live-work-travel-eu/coronavirus-response/travel-during-coronavirus-pandemic-0/common-approach-travel-measures-eu_en

Current information on disease progress, travel restrictions, testing requirements etc. for countries in the EU is contained in a website/app <https://reopen.europa.eu/en> and is particularly pertinent for coming tourism requirements.

COUNCIL OF EUROPE

The Council of Europe has a number of relevant programmes, but also works with the UN and EU in some of their programmes.

Examples include:

The European Charter for Regional or Minority Languages protects and promotes languages used by traditional minorities. <https://www.coe.int/en/web/european-charter-regional-or-minority-languages/about-the-charter>

Cultural Routes of the Council of Europe <https://www.coe.int/en/web/cultural-routes/home>

UNITED NATIONS

The wide-ranging programmes of the United Nations have influenced many national and regional approaches. Amongst these are:

Agenda 2030 - The Sustainable Development Goals (<https://sdgs.un.org>)

'Culture' is specifically identified in SDG11 with an aim to safeguard the world's cultural and natural heritage, but as a cross-cutting theme it also impacts

- environment and resilience
- prosperity and livelihoods
- policies for sustainable tourism
- knowledge and skills,
- inclusion and participation

WORLD TOURISM ORGANISATION (UNWTO - <http://www.unwto.org/>)

The Organisation's main priorities are:

- Mainstreaming tourism in the global agenda
- Improving tourism competitiveness
- Promoting sustainable tourism development
- Advancing tourism's contribution to poverty reduction and development
- Fostering knowledge, education and capacity building
- Building partnership

UNESCO <https://en.unesco.org/>

UNESCO'S World Heritage Sites <http://whc.unesco.org/en/list/>

Sites must be of outstanding universal value and meet at least one out of ten selection criteria.

UNESCO'S Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity

<https://ich.unesco.org/en/lists>

Celebration of oral tradition and expression, crafts, knowledge and practice on nature and the universe, social practices, rituals and festivals, performing arts.

ORGANISATION FOR ECONOMIC CO-OPERATION AND DEVELOPMENT (OECD)

<http://www.oecd.org>

The OECD has, in the light of coronavirus issues, instituted a specific interest in cultural and creative sectors as vehicles for local development.

EUROPEAN TRAVEL COMMISSION

The European Travel Commission (ETC) is the non-profit organisation responsible for the promotion of Europe as a tourist destination in third markets. 33 National Tourism Organisations work together to build the value of tourism across Europe through cooperation in sharing best practices, market intelligence and promotion. <https://etc-corporate.org>

Appendix B Arrangements For Round Tables By Partners

Description of organisation of round tables

Art Nouveau, Barcelona, Spain

Due to the surge in coronavirus cases in Barcelona and the resultant restrictions on in-person gatherings that were in place during the spring and early summer of 2021, it was considered prudent to hold the roundtable meeting online. Several of the University's contacts in the local and regional government and tourism sectors were unable or unwilling to participate in an online event due to pressure of work. In general, participants displayed a **high degree of consensus** on all topics covered.

Buzau Carpathians and Sub-Carpathians, Romania

Responses follow a large face-to-face round table organised in the study area which gathered a satisfactory number of participants, considering the pandemic context. The round table covered national, regional and local stakeholders.

The Cyclades, Greece

Although UAegean has enlisted about 12 (mostly official) stakeholders, unfortunately only 4 of them responded positively to the doodle invitation of our call and, due to technical problems, only 3 were finally able to participate in the round table, as shown above. A series of technical problems came up in the duration of the round table, which were mostly successfully dealt with.

Ida-Virumaa, Estonia

It was not possible to organise face-to-face round tables, so responses were gained by a series of online and in-person interviews with tourism entrepreneurs and representatives of cultural institutions in urban and rural areas. There was strong enthusiasm shown by participants.

Kinderdijk, Netherlands

The stakeholders were all genuinely committed to quality tourism. A physical round table was held with three stakeholders, two stakeholders were consulted by phone.

Komárom, Hungary/ Komárno, Slovakia

In order to avoid problems that may rise during border crossing the team decided to organise the Stakeholder round tables separately with partners from Komárom and Komárno. The team is in constant contact with all of the listed participants and they were highly motivated to discuss matters related to cultural tourism in the area.

Lusatia, Germany

Stakeholder contacts were organised as individual online expert interviews – face-to-face was felt to be inadvisable for COVID-19 reasons. Engagement of stakeholders described as 'satisfactory'.

Ljubljana, Slovenia

The team organised 9 individual interviews with a variety of stakeholders involved in tourism/culture sector – most of whom are Ljubljana residents. Five interviews were done in person, four took place on-line via the MS Teams application.

The Valley of Palaces and Gardens (Lower Silesia, Poland)

For a range of reasons, including the pandemic precautions, it was not possible to organize a round table meeting. Therefore, it was decided to conduct individual interviews. The research technique used was individual in-depth interview. With the exception of one held by video conference, the meetings were personal and enthusiastic engagement was experienced – out of 12 potential stakeholders approached, 10 took part in the activity.

Media Tourism, Scotland UK

Responses were collected through a series of meetings with stakeholders on an individual basis. Information gathered, together with a film describing both SPOT and the location, was fed into two round tables for discussion in November.

Nitra, Slovakia

Altogether 25 stakeholders were contacted, of which 16 submitted their responses or took part in the discussions. Two stakeholder round tables were held in August and September, and some of the stakeholders requested background materials for the discussion, and they responded individually.

Piedmont Landscape and Literary Park, Italy

The first round table was attended by two stakeholders (a financial initiative for tourism called other intended attendees and interestingly, the round table addressed a number of financial aspects). A second round table involved 3 actors in the cultural sector; the third was expected to deal with big events but finally involved actors engaged in different sectors such as the official body protecting the wine identity and a festival that enhance small villages. A fourth round table involved some of the mayors of the municipalities that are stakeholders of the UNESCO site of the Vineyard Landscape of Piedmont: Langhe-Roero and Monferrato, together with the site Director.

Southern Moravia, Czechia

Enthusiastic engagement with SPOT was reported.

The first round table was organized in a hybrid form (online and onsite at MENDELU), however, an online part had to be cancelled during the meeting due to a technical problem.

Second: The two stakeholders participated personally and one online. Third: Five stakeholders participated personally and one online.

Styrian Iron Route, Austria

The University of Graz conducted face-to face interviews with four key representatives active in the field of cultural tourism in the case-study region. As the region is rather small, some of the

stakeholders interviewed, hold multiple functions in more than one institution. The interviews loosely follow the material discussed in the project group and prepared by the WP2 leader. One interview had two interviewees present.

Beit She'an Valley, Israel

Face-to-face interviews were held with 7 stakeholders. This was followed by a round table discussion with 9 participants.

Appendix C List of Stakeholders

Art Nouveau, Barcelona, Spain

Dr. Eugeni Osácar Marzal	CETT Barcelona School of Tourism, Hospitality, and Gastronomy	Director of Research
Francesc Solé Parellada	Fundación Conocimiento y Desarrollo (CYD Foundation) and 7 Portes restaurant	Vice President of Foundation and Restaurant Owner
Josep Tardà Jorba	Sant Pau Modernist Complex	Director of Communications and Institutional Relations
Amilcar Vargas	Casa Batlló	Responsible for implementation of the UNESCO World Heritage Convention in Casa Batlló.
Dr. Montserrat Pareja-Eastaway	University of Barcelona	Director, Master in Cultural Management; GRC, Creativity, Innovation & Urban Transformation

Buzau Carpathians and Sub-Carpathians, Romania

Furtună Daniela	Colti City Hall	Inspector
Ciobanu Adrian	County Centre of Culture and Arts Buzău	Deputy Director
Boicu Geanina	Cislău City Hall	Inspector
Cernat Alina	Pătărlagele City Hall	Inspector
Bob Ion Marin	Merei City Hall	Public Administrator
Bobrotă Anca Mariana	Lopătari City Hall	Referee
Stoica Nicolae	Pănătău City Hall	Mayor
Mihai Daniel	Pârscov City Hall	Mayor
Cojocă Dragos	Buzău County Council - Regional Development Department	Executive Director
Preda Vali	Buzău County Council	Councillor
Stâlpeanu Anca	Buzău County Council	Councillor
Haret Loredana	Buzău County Council	Councillor
Drăgulescu Gabriela	Buzău County Council	Councillor
Cristina Partal	National Association of Rural, Eco and Cultural Tourism in Romania - ANTREC Buzău	President
Nicolae Liliana	Buzău County Council	Executive Director
Tescaru Mihaela	Buzău County Council	Councillor
Iordache Alina	Buzău County Council	Councillor
Mocănută Claudiu	Buzău County Council	Councillor
Vasile Dobrita	County Directorate for Culture, Buzău	Councillor
Sava Flavia	Buzău County Council	Councillor
Gilmeanu Nicoleta	Buzău County Council	Tourism Advisor

Badea Sebastian	Buzău County Council	Councillor
Mihăică Daniel	Năeni Territorial Administration	General Secretary
Damian Nicoleta	Institute of Geography, Romanian Academy	Senior Researcher
Paul Serban	Institute of Geography, Romanian Academy	Researcher
Mihailov Luminița	South-East Regional Development Agency	General Director
Neagu Petre Emanoil	Buzău County Council	President
Stoica Alexandru	Buzău County Council	Public Administrator
Irina Cozma	Ministry of Development, Public Works, and Administration	Councillor
Irena Mocanu	Institute of Geography, Romanian Academy	Senior Researcher
Dan Bălțeanu	Institute of Geography, Romanian Academy	Director
Mitrică Bianca	Institute of Geography, Romanian Academy	Senior Researcher
Ines Grigorescu	Institute of Geography, Romanian Academy	Senior Researcher
Monica Dumitrascu	Institute of Geography, Romanian Academy	Deputy Director

The Cyclades, Greece

Dimitris Athanassoulis (DA)	Cyclades Ephorate of Antiquities	Director (Ephor) of Antiquities (Cyclades)
Maria Psarrou (MP)	National Greek Tourism Organisation (EOT)	Senior Executive, Audio Visual, Media and Production Department—Division of Tourism Promotion (Andros)
Antonis Maragkos (AM)	Cyclades Chamber of Commerce	Head of the Department of Development and Documentation (Syros)

Ida-Virumaa, Estonia

Grete Habakukk	Alutaguse Huvikeskus	cultural work coordinator
Ingrid Spitz	Alutaguse Huvikeskus	director
Etti Kagarov	Estonian Mining Museum	director
Johanna Rannula	Narva Art Residency	director (as of 1. October 2021)
Jaanus Mikk	Narva Gate	CEO
Serafima Kolodkina	Vaba Lava Narva	producer
Rene Abramson	Vaba Lava Narva	sales manager
Piia Tamm	Jõhvi Concert Hall Virus Film Fund	director (2005-2021) coordinator
Egle Rääsk	VR Blueray	Head of VR
Priit Orav	Freelance tourism entrepreneur	Guesthouse owner, tour guide
Ainar Varinurm	Kohtla-Järve Museum of Oil Shale	Director
Jekaterina Muravyova	Sinimägede Muuseumi Sihtasutus Vaivara Blue Hills Museum/Narva-Jõesuu Local History Museum	Employee

Jelena Antusheva	Sillamäe Museum	Advertisement and PR Manager
Olga Eskor	Sillamäe Town Government	Information and Marketing Specialist (2018–2021)

Kinderdijk, Netherlands

Peter-Jan van Steenberg	SWEK (<i>Stichting Werelderfgoed Kinderdijk</i> , Foundation World Heritage Kinderdijk)	Director
Peter Paul Klapwijk	Private consultant	Miller, volunteer, activist
Richard Slagboom	Arvalis Natuuradvies	Independent ecologist, educator
Eric Spaans	Private management consultant	Programme manager Kinderdijk
	Municipality Alblasserdam	Strategic advisor and teamlead Spatial Development
Marcel Pleijte	Wageningen Research	discussant
Bas Pedroli	Wageningen Research	discussant

Komárom/Komárno, Hungary/Slovakia

Round Table 1 Komárom

Nóra Szili Somogyiné	Fortress of Monostor	Cultural and Tourism Director
Zoltán Bara	Ponsdanubii EGTC	Managing director
Tamás Proczellei	The Komárom City Marketing and Tourism Nonprofit Ltd.	Representative member
Éva Happ	Széchenyi István University, Tourism Department	Head of Department

Round Table 2 Komárno

Terézia Kelemen	Ferenc Lehár Civil Association	Director
József Csütörtöky	Danube Museum	Director
Róbert Lakatos	Béni Egressy Municipal Cultural Centre (VMK)	Director
István Domián	Celemantia Roman Camp Izsa	Director, Mayor of Izsa municipality
Andrej Ozimy	Komárno Municipal Office, Department of Culture, Tourism and Monument Protection of the Municipal Office, Fortress of Komárno	Department Director, Director of the Fortress of Komárno

Lusatia, Germany

Jana Lopper	Tourism Development Agency Lieberose / Oberspreewald	Managing Director
Bernd Boschan	Administrative District Lieberose / Oberspreewald	Director
Rainer Hilgenfeld	Municipality of Schwielochsee	Mayor
Carola Köhler	Landkreis (District) Dahme-Spreewald, Dept. Reg. Development, Economy and Tourism	Chief Officer

Martin Linsen	Brandenburg Ministry of Economy, Labour and Energy, Dept. of Tourism	Chief Officer
Dominik Rein	I.N.A. Lieberoser Heide Ltd	Project Manager
Annemarie Kaiser	Foundation "Natural Landscapes Brandenburg"	Project Coordinator
Frau Konzack	Hotel Spreewaldhof Romantik	Owner
Melanie Kossatz	Spreewald Association	President
Annette Ernst	Spreewald Tourism Association	Manager
Inka Thunecke	Verein der Freunde des Rohkunstbau e.V.	Board and Organisation of art exhibitions in the Lieberose castle

Ljubljana, Slovenia

(Participants anonymised)	Public institution: museum or gallery in Ljubljana	Marketing and development
"	Private business: local food and beverage store	Owner and head of sales
"	Self-employed private business	Local "independent" tourist guide
"	Public agency: Ljubljana Tourism (TL)	Marketing and development
"	Programme of a public institution of the Museum of Architecture and Design, a supporting platform for CCIs – Centre for Creativity (The CzK Platform)	Project leader, researcher
"	Public institution: museum or gallery in Ljubljana	Marketing and development
"	Private business: shop with local products and souvenirs made by Slovenian artisans	Owner and head of sales
"	Public agency: Slovenian Tourism Board (STB)	Marketing and development
"	Public institution: Ministry of Culture	Official; expertise in cultural heritage

The Valley of Palaces and Gardens (Lower Silesia, Poland)

Piotr Wnukowicz	Department of Tourism Lower Silesia Marshal's Office (<i>Wydział Turystyki, Urząd Marszałkowski Województwa Dolnośląskiego</i>)	Director of the Department of Tourism
Jakub Feiga	Lower Silesian Tourist Organization (<i>Dolnośląska Organizacja Turystyczna</i>)	Director of the Management Board Office
Agnieszka Łętkowska	Lower Silesian Association of Landscape Parks (<i>Dolnośląski Zespół Parków Krajobrazowych</i>)	Deputy <i>Director</i>
Grzegorz Truchanowicz	Municipal Office in Mysłakowice (<i>Urząd Gminy Mysłakowice</i>)	Deputy of the Commune Head
Katarzyna Smorek	Palaces and Gardens of Jelenia Gora Valley Foundation	Promotion Specialist

	<i>(Fundacja Doliny Pałaców i Ogrodów)</i>	
Janusz Korzeń	Karkonosze Foundation (<i>Fundacja Karkonoska</i>) Karkonosze Society (<i>Towarzystwo Karkonoskie</i>)	Co-founder and President of the Foundation and the Society
Dorota Goetz	Local Action Group "Partnerstwo Ducha Gór" (<i>Lokalna Grupa Działania "Partnerstwo Ducha Gór"</i>)	President of the LAG
Bożena Danielska	Karkonosze Museum in Jelenia Góra (<i>Muzeum Karkonoskie w Jeleniej Górze</i>)	Acting Director
Piotr Gryszel	Polish Tourist and Sightseeing Society – Western Sudetes Branch (<i>Polskie Towarzystwo Turystyczno-Krajoznawcze - Oddział „Sudety Zachodnie”</i>)	President of the Branch
Elisabeth von Küster	Cultural Landscape Development Foundation – Dominium Łomnica (<i>Fundacja Rozwoju Krajobrazu Kulturowego – Dominium Łomnica</i>)	Co-founder and President of the Foundation, The owner of the Łomnica palace

Media Tourism, Scotland UK

Jenni Steele	Visit Scotland	
	Scottish Tourism Alliance	
Samuel Wilson	Historic Environment Scotland	Digital Content Officer
Douglas Wilson	HES Doune	
Murray Pittock	National Trust for Scotland	
Micheal Terwey	National Trust for Scotland	Head of Heritage and Consultancy
Philip Long	National Trust for Scotland	CEO
Gordon Morrison	AVTEF	
Ilsa Finlay	Great Tapestry of Scotland	Bookings
Sandy	Great Tapestry of Scotland	Manager
Sarah MacDonald	South of Scotland Destination Alliance	
Giles Ingram	Abbotsford Trust	
Euan Jardine	Scottish Borders Council	
Tracey Alder	Galashiels Community Council	
Dougie Johnston	Galashiels Community Council	

	Galashiels and Melrose Chamber of Commerce	
Laura	Old Gala House	
Chris Wymess	MacArts Centre	
	Energise Galashiels	
Rob Claridge	Live Borders	Head of marketing
Neven and Fabiano	Creative Borders	Owners
Ben MacCorquodale	Kilmadock Development Trust	Member
Pamela	douneanddeanston.com	Web designer
Bob	Doune	Business proprietor
Martin Earl	Stirling Council	Councillor
Evelyn Tweed	Member of the Scottish Parliament	
Karen Ross	Doune Community Council	
Steve McLeish	Independent Tour Operator	
Ken	Heritage Centre	

Nitra, Slovakia

Zuzana Palenčíková	Department of Tourism, Faculty of Central European Studies, Constantine the Philosopher University in Nitra	Education of future professionals – managers in tourism (for the Hospitality sector and Destination Management)
Marta Hároníková	Nitra Tourism Organization	Marketing, promotion and support of tourism in Nitra
Jaroslav Dóczy	Andrej Bagar Theater in Nitra	Provision of cultural services (theater performances) and organization of international (Central) European festival Divadelná Nitra
Ivona Fraňová	Association of Information Centers of Slovakia (AICES)	AICES is an interest association of natural and legal persons operating in the field of information and tourism. The aim is to connect the tourist information centers in Slovakia, improve the provision of services to tourists in mutual coordination on the basis of established standards, and generally improve the situation in Slovak tourism.
Terézia Zaujecová	Nitra Tourist Information Center	Support and develop tourism in Nitra and its surroundings, make Nitra an attractive destination for domestic and foreign tourists
Adriana Skovajová	Hotel LUX	Operator – provider of hospitality and catering services

Milan Klč	Hotel Mikado	Operator – provider of hospitality and catering services
Daniel Balko	Medieval Taverna in Nitra	Operator – provider of catering services
Ján Kratochvíl	Zobor Embellishment Association	NGO – preservation of cultural values
Ľubica Lachká	Nitra Community Foundation	Provider of grants to support community activities
Tibor Ujľacký	European Cultural Route of St. Cyril and Methodius in the Nitra Self-Governing Region	Establishment of this certified European route as a tool for the preservation and presentation of Cyril and Methodius' cultural and spiritual heritage, and as a tourism product.
Marek Civiň	ARRIVA Nitra, a.s. (transport company)	Transport of cultural tourists
Irena Lehocká	Nitra 2026 Association	Management of activities within the European Capital of Culture project
Anna Rusňáková Martin Jančovič	Ponitrie Protected Landscape Area	Protection of natural and cultural values of the Tribeč mountain range in the city of Nitra and its hinterland
Veronika Bilicová	Matica Slovenská Nitra	Cultivation and preservation of cultural, ideological and historical traditions for the existence and future of the Slovak Republic. As the only institution in Slovakia, Matica Slovenská massively maintains and realistically develops the national and spiritual pillars of our state.
Dagmar Bojďová	Nitra City Hall – Department of Culture	Management of activities in cultural tourism

Piedmont Landscape and Literary Park, Italy

Round Table 1

Participant anonymised	Associazione Amici di castelli aperti	Founder
Aldo Buzio	Associazione Turismo in Langa	Managing Director

Round Table 2

Bianca Roagna	Centro Studi di Letteratura, Storia, Arte e Cultura Beppe Fenoglio	Director
Roberta Ceretto	Ceretto Aziende Vitivinicole S.r.l.	Owner
Alessandra Muratore	Barolo & Castles Foundation	Coordinator

Round Table 3

Mauro Carbone	ATL Ente Turismo Langhe Monferrato and Roero	Director
Paola Farinetti	Attraverso Festival	Artistic Coordinator
Andrea Ferrero	Consorzio di tutela Barolo Barbaresco Alba Langhe e Dogliani	Director

Round Table 4

Roberto Cerrato	Paesaggi vitivinicoli di Langhe-Roero and	Director
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	Monferrato site UNESCO	
Renata Bianco	Barolo	Mayor
Annalisa Ghella	Neive	Mayor
Livio Genesisio	Monforte d'Alba	Mayor

Southern Moravia, Czechia

Round Table 1

Mgr. Bc. Pavlína Komínková	Muzeum Blanenska	director
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Round Table 2

Zdeněk Šmýd	Touristic Association Slovácko	manager
Ing. Ivana Lukášková	Division of Regional Development, Department of Tourism, Regional office of South Moravia	head of the department
Mgr. Vít Hrdoušek	LAG Strážnicko	project manager

Round Table 3

Ass. Prof. Ing. Kateřina Ryglová, Ph.D.	Department of Marketing and Trade, Mendel University in Brno	Academic staff - associate professor: Tourism, Business in tourism, Marketing
Mgr. Ing. Jaromír Jurka	Secondary school Brno, Charbulova, Member of APČ	Teacher: hospitality and tourism, career advisor of the Gastronomy section, accredited tourist guide
Ing., Arch., Lenka Štěpánková	BVV Trade Fairs Brno	Protection of architectural heritage
Ing. Jaroslav Bílek	BVV Trade Fairs Brno	Head of Marketing and Communications office
Ass. Prof. Mgr. Ondřej Konečný, Ph.D.	Local Action Group (LAG) Brána Vysočiny, Faculty of Regional Development and International Studies: Mendel University	Chairman of the Vysočina Gate LAG, Head of the Department of Regional Development
Bc. Jaroslava Hrušková	South Moravian Region - Department of Regional Development	Tourism officer in the Department of Regional Development

Styrian Iron Route, Austria

Gerfried Tiffner	Erz&Eisen GmbH + LEADER Management Steirische Eisenstrasse	Regional development, tourism provider
Susanne Leitner-Böchzelt	Head of Museum Centre Leoben + Board of the regional tourism marketing organisation 'Hochsteiermark'	Cultural tourism, Tourism marketing (regional)
Robert Herzog	Tourism association Leoben	Tourism marketing (local)
Erich Neuhold	Tourism Steiermark	Tourism marketing (state)

Beit She'an Valley, Israel

Ofira Segev	Springs Valley Regional Council	Spokeswoman
Anat Dagan	Transitions programme	Regional Council representative
Jaque Levi	Town of Beit She'an	Mayor
Ezra Pery	Town of Beit She'an	Spokesman
Dror Segal	Kibbutz Nir David Museum	Manager
Oved Yevin	South Jordan Drainage Authority	Director
Nirit Bagron	Gesher Yard heritage site	Manager
	Coffee shop at kibbutz Gesher	
	Field school Alon Tavor	
	Renewable Energy Tourist Educational Center	Kibbutz Ma'ale Gilboa
	MakKale - Gifts and glass-making workshops	Kibbutz Tirat Zvi
	Sde Nahum carpentry workshops	
	Bio-tour	Kibbutz Sde Eliyahu
Anat Dagan	Regional Council	Tourism initiatives support
Offira Segev	Regional Council	Spokeswoman
	Regional Council	Assistant to Anat Dagan